

1. Title Page

Title	Effect of nurse and midwifery staffing on breastfeeding and the healthy newborn at hospital discharge – a target trial emulation protocol
Research question & Objectives	Investigate the causal effect of nurse and midwifery staffing levels on the rate of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge and the discharge of a healthy newborn.
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Conflict of interest	None

Disclaimer: This target trial emulation protocol builds on a previously published protocol (1) and some parts overlap strongly. The published protocol is freely available on Zenodo and is seen as the core document. Both studies work with data from the same clinical site and the same time frame.

The template used for this protocol was published by Wang and colleagues (2).

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2. Abstract

Studies' authors have suggested that midwifery staffing is associated with the likelihood of women breastfeeding exclusively at hospital discharge (3). In the labour ward, the gold standard for midwifery staffing is one-to-one care during established labour and birth. In postnatal units, however, no such recommendation exists and standards for staffing are lacking (4). Some countries have introduced target midwife-to-mother-baby-dyad ratios (5,6). The objective of this study, using target trial methodology, is to investigate the causal effect of recommended staffing ratios compared to less than recommended staffing on the likelihood of successful breastfeeding at hospital discharge and the likelihood of discharging a healthy newborn.

The causal question of this target trial is to determine the effect of receiving full target ratio nursing and midwifery care during the hospital stay on the postnatal unit until discharge on the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding / healthy newborn. The target trial is emulated with routine hospital data from one tertiary hospital from 01. January 2019 to 31. December 2022. The exposure – target ratio nurse and midwifery staffing – is defined as receiving target ratio staffing during the whole stay on the postnatal unit until discharge home for 100% or for less than 100% of the time. The eligibility criteria are assessed at admission to the postnatal unit. For exclusive breastfeeding, inpatient adult women who have given birth in the same institution and were transferred directly from the labour ward to the postnatal unit are eligible. For evaluating the healthy newborn, inpatient newborns, born in the same institution, always together with their mother before admission to the postnatal unit are eligible. Women who had medical reasons or decided to suppress lactation will be excluded. Readmissions to the postnatal unit will be excluded. Mothers and newborns in all comparison groups are assumed to be comparable conditional on selected baseline covariates. For both outcomes we identified, *gestational age*, *parity*, *birth weight*, *maternal age*, *maternal country of birth*, *mode of birth*, *labour complications*, *pregnancy complications* and *neonatal risk of hypoglycaemia* as confounding variables. For the outcome healthy newborn, we consider one additional confounding variable, namely the *feeding method*. To adjust for confounding and derive the total effect, we use g-methods. To assess robustness with respect to different misspecifications we consider both marginal structural models fitted by means of inverse probability weighting and the g-formula. Ethical approval to access the routine hospital data has been granted by the local ethics committee [2024-00300].

3. Amendments and updates

Version date	Version number	Section of protocol	Amendment or update	Reason
13.03.2025	1.0	All	Initiation of protocol	
30.05.2025	1.0	All	Finalisation of first draft	

4. Milestones

Table 1 Milestones

Milestone	Date
Initial protocol, Draft 1	13.03.2025
Assessment of expected precision and diagnostic evaluations complete	March – April 2025
Protocol Amendment	-
Publication of Protocol	30.05.2025

5. Rationale and background

What is known about the condition: Human milk is considered the best nutrition for a newborn baby and breastfeeding is associated with increased bonding and improved maternal and child health (7,8). Breastfeeding exclusively is recommended by the World Health Organization for the first six months, with partial breastfeeding recommended until two years of age (9). Breastfeeding success depends on multiple factors such as health and wellbeing of the mother, health and wellbeing of the child, breastfeeding initiation and many more (10,11). It has been shown that breastfeeding initiation and first days of breastfeeding, in particular, are strongly correlated with longer duration of exclusive breastfeeding (10). The newborn has to adapt to extrauterine life immediately after birth, with the first 48 hours being the most vulnerable period (12,13). During this time, the newborn body needs to regulate body temperature and stabilise blood sugar levels independently and in conjunction with feeding. These adaptations can be supported by optimal care. Ensuring warm body temperature through skin-to-skin contact with a parent and applying sufficient warming cloths when the newborn is in its own bed. Feeding regularly also helps ensure stable blood glucose levels. These two measures support the physiological development of the newborn and help prevent the need for admission to a neonatal intensive care unit (12,14).

What is known about the exposure of interest: The current staffing practices on postnatal units demonstrate large variation between countries with some recommending a ratio of 1:4 for the mother-baby-dyad and others stating a minimal standard of 1:3 (5,6). A peculiarity of postnatal units is that newborns are almost never counted as individual patients. A staffing ratio of 1:4 essentially means caring for eight individuals (4 mothers + 4 newborns). The mentioned measures to ensure well adaptation of the newborn as well as supporting the breastfeeding initiation are directly linked with workforce.

Gaps in knowledge: It is unclear, how the workforce on the postnatal unit influences exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge and assures a healthy newborn (15). It is further unclear, which staffing ratio can promote these outcomes.

What is the expected contribution of this study? Knowing which staffing ratio promotes breastfeeding and a healthy newborn, this can be implemented in the hospitals to increase breastfeeding rates, which is correlated with less rehospitalisations and thus lower costs for society. Less newborns needing neonatal intensive care increase the parental mental well-being as well as saving hospital costs.

6. Research question and objectives

Table 2 Two primary research questions and objectives

A. First research question and objective

Objective:	Investigate the causal effect of nurse and midwifery staffing on the establishment of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge.
Hypothesis:	The higher the staffing levels, the higher the proportion of women with exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge.
Population (mention key inclusion-exclusion criteria):	Inclusion: All women that give birth in the same institution and stay for the early postpartum period on the postnatal unit (usually 3-5 days after birth). Exclusion: Readmission; stillbirth; suppressed lactation; separation from child before admission to postnatal unit; age <18 years; multiple birth
Exposure:	100% of the time of target nurse-to-patient ratio during stay on postnatal unit. (Target ratios are defined in the section <i>setting</i>).
Comparator:	Less than 100% of the time of target nurse-to-patient ratio during stay on postnatal unit
Outcome:	Exclusive breastfeeding during the last 24 hours before hospital discharge.
Time (when follow up begins and ends):	Follow-up begins at admission to the postnatal unit (directly from labour ward after birth), ends at discharge from the postnatal unit.
Setting:	Tertiary hospital, women's clinic, postnatal unit (inpatient). Staffed with registered nurses (RNs), registered midwives (RMs), working in a three-shift system Target nurse-to-patient ratio based on international regulations (5): Day shift (07:00 – 15:54): 1 to 4 (mother-baby-dyad)* Late shift (14:30 – 23:24): 1 to 4 Night shift (22:30 – 07:24): 1 to 6 *mother-baby-dyad results in two patients, though international regulations often don't count the child as separate patient.
Main measure of effect:	Relative risks / Risk difference.

B. Second research question and objective

Objective:	Investigate the causal effect of nurse and midwifery staffing on the promotion of a healthy newborn at hospital discharge.
Hypothesis:	The higher the staffing levels, the higher the proportion of newborns being healthy at hospital discharge
Population (<i>mention key inclusion-exclusion criteria</i>):	Inclusion: All newborns that are born in the same institution and stay for the early postpartum period on the postnatal unit (usually 3-5 days after birth). Exclusion: Readmission; stillbirth; separation from mother before admission to postnatal unit; multiple birth
Exposure:	100% of time of target nurse-to-patient ratio during stay on postnatal unit. (Target ratios are defined in the section <i>setting</i>).
Comparator:	Less than 100% of time of target nurse-to-patient ratio during stay on postnatal unit
Outcome:	Healthy newborn defined as a composite outcome consisting of 1) always normal temperature, 2) normal glucose levels [if measured], 3) physiological jaundice [if measured], 4) always together with their mother.
Time (<i>when follow up begins and ends</i>):	Follow-up begins at admission to the postnatal unit (directly from labour ward after birth), ends with hospital discharge or first event of complication (hypothermia, hypoglycaemia, hyperbilirubinaemia needing phototherapy, admission to neonatal intensive care unit)
Setting:	Tertiary hospital, women's clinic, postnatal unit (inpatient). Staffed with RNs, RMs, working in a three-shift system Target nurse-to-patient ratio based on international regulations (5): Day shift (07:00 – 15:54): 1 to 4 (mother-baby-dyad)* Late shift (14:30 – 23:24): 1 to 4 Night shift (22:30 – 07:24): 1 to 6 *mother-baby-dyad results in two patients, though international regulations often don't count the child as separate patient.
Main measure of effect:	Relative risks / Risk difference.

7. Research methods

7.1. Study design

Research design (e.g. cohort, case-control, etc.): Cohort study

Rationale for study design choice: To establish the causal effect of different staffing levels a randomised controlled trial would be the first choice of study design. However, implementing different staffing levels is not ethical and practically not feasible. Though in a cohort study, different staffing levels occur naturally due to the clustering effect of births and a resulting high variation in care demand with only limited adjustment of the staffing supply side (16). A formal causal inference framework guides the cohort study investigators to adjust for known confounding to estimate the effect, while reducing the risk of bias.

7.2. Study design diagram

Cohort Entry Date
(Admission to postnatal unit)
Day 0

Inclusion Assessment Window
(Inpatient, Consent, Electronic health record entry)
Days [Birth, 0]

Exclusion Assessment Window
(Stillbirth, Readmission, Suppressed lactation, Maternal age < 18, Multiple birth)
Days [Birth, 0]

Exposure Assessment Window
[0,0]

Assignment at admission
Evaluation until discharge / outcome occurs

Covariate Assessment Window
(Baseline conditions)
Days [Birth, 0]

Follow-up Window
Days [0, Hospital discharge]

7.3. Setting

7.3.1 Context and rationale for definition of time 0 (and other primary time anchors) for entry to the study population

Time 0 is defined by the date and time when the mother and her newborn are admitted to the postnatal unit directly after birth from the labour ward to stay for the early postpartum period (3-5 days). At admission, mothers and their newborns are assigned together (mother-baby-dyad) a specific amount of care based on available staffing.

Table 3 Operational Definition of Time 0 (index date) and other primary time anchors

Study population name(s)	Time Anchor Description (e.g. time 0)	Number of entries	Type of entry	Washout window	Care Setting ¹	Code Type ²	Diagnosis position	Incident with respect to...	Measurement characteristics/validation	Source of algorithm
Exposure: mother-baby-dyad receiving 100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio	Admission to hospital postnatal unit for early postpartum	Mothers: Single entry Newborn: Single entry	Incident	n/a	IP	n/a	n/a	Birth	n/a	Investigator review of staffing levels
Comparator: mother-baby-dyad receiving <100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio	Admission to hospital postnatal unit for early postpartum	Mothers: Single entry Newborn: Single entry	Incident	n/a	IP	n/a	n/a	Birth	n/a	Investigator review of staffing levels

¹ IP = inpatient, OP = outpatient, ED = emergency department, OT = other, n/a = not applicable

² See appendix A for listing of clinical codes for each study parameter

7.3.2 Context and rationale for study inclusion criteria:

All women who have given birth and stay in the same institution on the postnatal unit during the early postpartum period (usually 3-5 days after birth). They need to be transferred directly from the labour ward to the postnatal unit, are recorded in the hospital's patient flow system and have an electronic health record. All newborns need to have an eligible mother, being recorded in the hospital's flow system and have an electronic health record.

Table 4. Operational Definitions of Inclusion Criteria

Criterion	Details	Order of application	Assessment window	Care Settings ¹	Code Type ²	Diagnosis position ³	Applied to study populations:	Measurement characteristics/validation	Source for algorithm
Mother admitted to the postnatal unit for early postpartum	Admission to the postnatal unit directly after birth from labour ward	After	[Birth, 0]	IP	ICD10-GM	Any	Exposure: 100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio care Comparator: <100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio care	n/a	n/a
Newborn admitted to the postnatal unit for early postpartum	Admission to the postnatal unit directly after birth from labour ward	After	[Birth, 0]	IP	ICD10-GM	Any	Exposure: 100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio care Comparator: <100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio care	n/a	n/a

¹ IP = inpatient, OP = outpatient, ED = emergency department, OT = other, n/a = not applicable

² See appendix A for listing of clinical codes for each study parameter

7.3.3 Context and rationale for study exclusion criteria

Maternal readmissions to the postnatal unit are usually due to complications during the later postpartum period, e.g., infections of breasts, wounds, or uterus. The research question targets the establishment of exclusive breastfeeding in the early postpartum period, which excludes readmissions. Neonatal readmissions on the other hand can occur during the target maternal stay on the postnatal unit. In this setting, it is possible that the newborn is admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit either directly after birth, due to early adaptation complications, or from the postnatal unit due to late adaptation complications. These newborns might be transferred back to the postnatal unit after 1 or 2 days. Their first stay on the postnatal unit will be included, but not their second, because the outcome healthy newborn is defined as never being separated from their mother. If separation occurred in the first stay, follow-up is stopped at the first discharge from the postnatal unit.

Mothers with a stillbirth who were transferred to the postnatal unit are excluded because none of the outcomes of interest apply to them.

There are medical contraindications to breastfeeding, as well as maternal preferences not to breastfeed. In these cases, the outcome breastfeeding cannot occur. Therefore, for the outcome exclusive breastfeeding, all mothers that suppressed lactation directly after birth are excluded. This does not apply for the outcome healthy newborn.

All minor mothers (< 18 years of age) are excluded because of their vulnerability as well as due to the small number, impossibility to deidentify.

If a separation of the mother-baby-dyad occurred before the admission to the postnatal unit, these cases will also be excluded. The influencing factors of this separation are multifactorial and impossible to correctly adjust for in the analysis. Therefore, if the mother stayed on the intermediate care unit or intensive care unit after birth, the mother-baby-dyad is excluded.

Newborns who are twins or triplets are excluded because they are very likely to receive high levels of midwifery staffing irrespective of the availability of staff. Furthermore, there are too many unknown factors for twins and triplets that influence their health. For example, their health and needs differ, if they were monozygotic or dizygotic twins (17). The information if they were monozygotic or dizygotic is not available from the routine data.

Table 5. Operational Definitions of Exclusion Criteria

Criterion	Details	Order of application	Assessment window	Care Settings ¹	Code Type ²	Diagnosis position ³	Applied to study populations:	Measurement characteristics/ validation	Source for algorithm
Readmission	Second admission to the postnatal unit.	After	[Birth, 0]	IP	ICD10-GM	Any	Exposure: 100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio care Comparator: <100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio care	n/a	n/a
Stillbirth	ICD10-GM codes for birth of a non-living newborn	After	[Birth, 0]	IP	ICD10-GM	Any	Exposure: Comparator: As above	n/a	n/a
Suppressed lactation [only for outcome breastfeeding]	ICD10-GM code for suppressed lactation	After	[Birth, 0]	IP	ICD10-GM	Any	Exposure: Comparator: As above	n/a	n/a
Maternal age < 18 years	Minor mothers are excluded. Measurement at time of labour ward admission.	After	[Birth]	IP	n/a	n/a	Exposure: Comparator: As above	n/a	n/a
Mother-baby-dyad always together	Transfer times are equal between mother and newborn (admission & discharge).	After	[Birth, 0]	IP	n/a	n/a	Exposure: Comparator: As above	n/a	Investigator review of movement entries.
Multiple births	ICD10-GM codes for twins, triplets and more	After	[Birth,0]	IP	ICD10-GM	Any	Exposure: Comparator: As above	n/a	n/a

¹ IP = inpatient, OP = outpatient, ED = emergency department, OT = other, n/a = not applicable

² See appendix A for listing of clinical codes for each study parameter

7.4. Variables

7.4.1 Context and rationale for exposure(s) of interest

It has been investigated in cross-sectional studies, whether midwifery staffing has an influence on the likelihood of women breastfeeding exclusively at hospital discharge and a positive association was shown. Higher levels of midwifery staffing were associated with higher levels of breastfeeding and a higher likelihood of a healthy newborn at hospital discharge (3,18,19). Compared to the labour ward, where the international gold standard is one-to-one care, it is not internationally established, what optimal staffing would look like on the postnatal unit. Nevertheless, the State of Victoria (Australia) has implemented safe staffing regulations, where in each shift, the target midwife-to-mother-baby-dyad ratio is defined (5).

A potential reason for the design of previous studies may be that assigning different staffing levels is rarely done due to ethical and organisational reasons. Less than usual staffing is not ethical and more than usual staffing is financially not feasible. Current national and international developments in staffing reductions due to budgetary cutbacks need to be investigated on their effect on maternal and neonatal health.

Due to clustering effects of births, there is high variation in care demand and the hospital system is not flexible enough to address these variations (16). This results in a natural experiment of different levels of staffing. In this natural experiment, the exposure – target nurse-to-patient ratio – is defined as a binary variable indicating whether the woman received the target ratio staffing during the whole stay in the postnatal unit until discharge home or not.

Algorithm to define duration of exposure effect:

For the outcome exclusive breastfeeding, the exposure duration is defined as the time between admission to the postnatal unit after birth for early postpartum care and 24 hours before discharge from the postnatal unit.

For the outcome healthy newborn, the exposure duration is defined as the time between admission to the postnatal unit after birth for early postpartum care and either the occurrence of a complication or discharge from the postnatal unit.

Table 6. Operational Definitions of Exposure

Exposure group name(s)	Details	Washout window	Assessment Window	Care Setting ¹	Code Type ²	Diagnosis position ³	Applied to study populations:	Incident with respect to...	Measurement characteristics/ validation	Source of algorithm
Exposure: 100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio care	Nurse-to-patient ratio per shift in relation to target ratio per shift	n/a	[0,0]	IP	n/a	n/a	Exposure: 100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio care Comparator: <100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio care	Birth	n/a	Investigator defined – admission to postnatal unit, directly from labour ward
Comparator: <100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio care		n/a	[0,0]	IP	n/a	n/a	Exposure: 100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio care Comparator: <100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio care	Birth	n/a	Investigator defined – admission to postnatal unit, directly from labour ward

¹ IP = inpatient, OP = outpatient, ED = emergency department, OT = other, n/a = not applicable

² See appendix A for listing of clinical codes for each study parameter

7.4.2 Context and rationale for outcome(s) of interest

There is an association between staffing levels and exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge (18–20). In one national cross-sectional investigation, being a healthy newborn was also found to be associated with different levels of staffing (18). Breastfeeding is known to have protective effects for mothers and newborns and is the gold standard of newborn nutrition (7,8). Therefore, increased levels of breastfeeding are of individual and national interest to have a healthy population (9).

To assess how hospital staffing influences exclusive breastfeeding, the breastfeeding status at hospital discharge is of interest. The clinical setting holds the UNICEF “Baby-Friendly Hospital” quality label, which includes the assessment of breastfeeding at hospital discharge (21). Their evaluation differentiates between fully breastfed during the hospital stay, partly breastfed and not breastfed at all. If they were partly breastfed, they evaluate whether they were at least fully breastfed during the last 24 hours before discharge (22).

In cases of neonatal risk of hypoglycaemia, the hospital standard operating procedure states that the newborns need to be offered formula milk after breastfeeding as long as there is not enough human milk (5 ml/kg) (14). Therefore, all of these newborns are partly breastfed at the beginning of the hospital stay, to assure that the newborns never end up in a hypoglycaemia, which is most likely during the first 48 hours after birth (23,24). After this period and as soon as there is sufficient human milk available, formula feeding is no longer medically indicated. Therefore, we define exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge by the timeframe of the last 24 hours before discharge.

There are some known risk factors for newborns regarding hypoglycaemia, hypothermia and hyperbilirubinaemia. All these known risk factors are addressed through standard operating procedures in the postnatal unit. Therefore, if adherence to these standards is high, the prevalence of these pathologies should be rather rare. If staffing is not optimal, it might result in missed care, which results in these pathologies (3).

Table 7. Operational Definitions of Outcome

Outcome name	Details	Primary outcome?	Type of outcome	Washout window	Care Settings ¹	Code Type ²	Diagnosis Position ³	Applied to study populations:	Measurement characteristics/ validation	Source of algorithm
Exclusive breastfeeding within the last 24 hours before hospital discharge	Feeding entries within the last 24 hours before discharge need all be breastfeeding	Yes	Binary	n/a	IP	n/a	n/a	Exposure: 100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio care Comparator: <100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio care	n/a	Investigator defined based on breastfeeding entries in EHR**
Healthy newborn at hospital discharge	All temperature, glucose, and bilirubin entries are within the norm. No separation from mother (due to admission to NICU*)	Yes	Binary	n/a	IP	n/a	n/a	Exposure: 100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio care Comparator: <100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio care	n/a	Investigator defined based on entries in EHR for temperature, glucose levels and bilirubin measurements

¹ IP = inpatient, OP = outpatient, ED = emergency department, OT = other, n/a = not applicable

² See appendix A for listing of clinical codes for each study parameter

*Neonatal intensive care unit

** EHR = electronic health record

7.4.3 Context and rationale for follow up

The outcomes of interest both occur during the stay on the postnatal unit for early postpartum. Follow-up duration is therefore until hospital discharge from the postnatal unit or until a complication occurs (hypothermia, hypoglycaemia, hyperbilirubinaemia, admission to neonatal intensive care unit), whichever occurs first. To ensure that all cases are coded and closed, routine data is extracted at earliest 30 days after inpatient stay to await final coding.

Table 8. Operational Definitions of Follow Up

Follow up start	Admission to postnatal unit	
Follow up end¹	Select all that apply	Specify
Date of outcome	Yes	Breastfeeding: date and time of hospital discharge. Newborn: date and time of first complication
Date of death	No	
End of observation in data	Yes	Hospital discharge from postnatal unit
Day X following index date (specify day)	No	
End of study period (specify date)	No	
End of exposure (specify operational details, e.g. stockpiling algorithm, grace period)	Yes	Breastfeeding: ends 24 hours before hospital discharge Newborn: ends either at hospital discharge or at first occurrence of complication
Date of add to/switch from exposure (specify algorithm)	No	
Other date (specify)	No	

¹ Follow up ends at the first occurrence of any of the selected criteria that end follow up.

7.4.4 Context and rationale for covariates (confounding variables and effect modifiers, e.g. risk factors, comorbidities, comedICATIONS)

Based on expert knowledge and specific literature searches for each outcome, we drew directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) for each outcome separately. With the DAGs we created a visualisation of the underlying assumptions how exposure and outcome are related and which other covariates are relevant for this relationship and in which role (confounder, moderator, mediator). We followed a method described by Ferguson et al. (25) to develop a DAG based on literature and expert knowledge. For each DAG we assessed every edge (arrow) separately regarding their temporality (does the leading knot occur before the ending knot?), face validity (is it explainable with logic?), and recourse to theory (are there any studies supporting this?) (25). The full list of assessments is available in Appendix B. To identify all variables necessary for deconfounding the effect of the exposure on the outcome of interest, the DAGs serve as a visual aid.

We quote the description of how to interpret the DAG from a previous protocol (1):

“In Figure 1, each element of the DAG is explained. The blue nodes (ancestors of outcome) do not lead to confounding if left unadjusted for. Red nodes are those covariates that introduce confounding paths if unadjusted for. The browser version of dagitty shows a minimally sufficient adjustment set (26,27). Adjusting for these covariates, presented as white nodes, is sufficient to block all confounding paths of the effect of interest on the outcome. For the outcomes separately, we have created one DAG without any adjustment for confounding (Figure 2, Figure 4) and a second DAG (Figure 3, Figure 5) adjusting so that all confounding paths (red lines / biasing paths) are blocked. Black lines are neither a causal nor a biasing path. These paths indicate relationships that either do not interfere with the causal path or would interfere but are adjusted for confounding.”

Figure 1: Legend for DAGs drawn in dagitty (26,27)

The covariates, identified as candidates for deconfounding the effect of the exposure of interest on the outcome, are sufficient to block all confounding paths of the effect of staffing on exclusive breastfeeding (green lines, causal paths) and for the effect of staffing on the healthy newborn (green lines, causal paths). All covariates presented in the DAGs are explained in more detail in Table 9.

Covariates necessary for deconfounding:

Outcome: Exclusive breastfeeding	Outcome: Healthy newborn
Gestational age	Gestational age
Birth weight	Birth weight
Neonatal risk of hypoglycaemia	Neonatal risk of hypoglycaemia
Parity	Parity
Maternal age	Maternal age
Maternal country of birth	Maternal country of birth
Mode of birth	Mode of birth
Labour complications	Labour complications
Pregnancy complications	Pregnancy complications
	Feeding method (human milk vs. formula)

Figure 2: DAG1 for outcome – exclusive breastfeeding, without any adjustment for confounding, TSB = total serum bilirubin

Figure 3: DAG1 for outcome – exclusive breastfeeding, when adjusting for the variables in the white nodes, TSB = total serum bilirubin

Figure 4: DAG2 for outcome – healthy newborn, without any adjustment for confounding

Figure 5: DAG2 for outcome – healthy newborn, when adjusting for the variables in the white nodes

Table 9. Operational Definitions of Covariates

Characteristic	Details	Type of variable	Assessment window	Care Settings ¹	Code Type ²	Diagnosis Position ³	Applied to study populations:	Measurement characteristics/ validation	Source for algorithm
Birth weight	Weight measured directly after birth in grams	Continuous	[Birth, 0]	IP	EHR*	n/a	Exposure: 100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio care Comparator: <100% of time target nurse-to-patient ratio care	n/a	n/a
Maternal country of birth / ethnicity {Citizenship}	Country where the person currently has citizenship (self-reported)	Categorical (Swiss, European, Non-European)	[Birth, 0]	IP	n/a	n/a	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a
Maternal country of birth / ethnicity {Language}	Self-reported primary language	Binary (German, non-German)	[Birth, 0]	IP	n/a	n/a	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a
Feeding method	Newborn feeding method	Categorical (Fully breastfed, partly breast fed, formula fed)	[Birth, 0]	IP	EHR	n/a	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a
Gestational age	Gestational age in number of days at birth	Continuous	[Birth, 0]	IP	FSO**	Any	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a
Labour complications	Complications such as complicated perineal tear; prolonged labour; postnatal haemorrhage	Binary (yes, no)	[Birth, 0]	IP	ICD10-GM	Any	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a

Characteristic	Details	Type of variable	Assessment window	Care Settings ¹	Code Type ²	Diagnosis Position ³	Applied to study populations:	Measurement characteristics/validation	Source for algorithm
Maternal age	Age: Time 0 – date of birth/365	Continuous	[Birth, 0]	IP	n/a	n/a	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a
Mode of birth	Mode of birth	Categorical (spontaneous, vaginal-operative, planned and unplanned caesarean section)	[Birth, 0]	IP	ICD10-GM, CHOP	Any	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a
Parity	Number of children born exclusive of this birth	Continuous	[Birth, 0]	IP	FSO	n/a	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a
Pregnancy complications	Complications such as any kind of diabetes, all hypertensive disorders	Binary (yes, no)	[Birth, 0]	IP	ICD10-GM	Any	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a
Risk of hypoglycaemia	Neonatal risk of hypoglycaemia due to different reasons. Identified through proxy of feeding intervention.	Binary (yes, no)	[Birth, 0]	IP	EHR	n/a	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a
Admission to NICU	Neonatal intensive care unit admission (currently mediator)	Binary (yes, no)	[0, Discharge]	IP	n/a	n/a	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a
Breastfeeding initiation within 1 hour after birth	First breastfeeding within 1 hour after birth (Moderator)	Binary (yes, no)	[Birth, 0]	IP	EHR	n/a	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a
Early skin-to-skin contact after birth within 30min	Direct skin-to-skin contact after birth (Moderator, not measured)		[Birth, 0]	IP	n/a	n/a	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a

Characteristic	Details	Type of variable	Assessment window	Care Settings ¹	Code Type ²	Diagnosis Position ³	Applied to study populations:	Measurement characteristics/validation	Source for algorithm
Length of stay	Duration of entry to postnatal unit until discharge in days (currently mediator)	Continuous	[0, Discharge]	IP	EHR	n/a	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a
Level of education	Categories based on level of education (Moderator, not measured)	Categorical	[Birth,0]	IP	n/a	n/a	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a
Peak total serum bilirubin	Highest measured total serum bilirubin value in the newborn in mmol/L (Moderator)	Continuous	[0, Discharge]	IP	EHR	n/a	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a
Phototherapy	Phototherapy initiated on the postnatal unit (Moderator)	Binary (yes, no)	[0, Discharge]	IP	CHOP	any	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a
Cold season	Outside temperature during hospital stay (Moderator)	Continuous	[0, Discharge]	IP	n/a	n/a	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a
Time of birth	Day time vs. night time (Moderator)	Binary (day, night)	[Birth, 0]	IP	n/a	n/a	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a
Risk of hypothermia	Different reasons for risk of hypothermia (Moderator, not measured)	Binary (yes, no)	[Birth, 0]	IP	n/a	n/a	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a
Risk of hyperbilirubinaemia	Different reasons for risk of hyperbilirubinaemia (Moderator, not measured)	Binary (yes, no)	[Birth, 0]	IP	n/a	n/a	Exposure: Comparator:	n/a	n/a

¹ IP = inpatient, OP = outpatient, ED = emergency department, OT = other, n/a = not applicable

² See appendix A for listing of clinical codes for each study parameter

* EHR = electronic health record

** FSO = federal statistical office

7.5. Data analysis

7.5.1 Context and rationale for analysis plan

We aim to estimate the effect of the exposure, which is 100% target nurse-to-patient ratio of care for the entire postnatal stay duration, on the establishment of exclusive breastfeeding compared to the natural exposure which is less than 100% of target nurse-to-patient ratio care. Identical to the previous published protocol, the per protocol effect where participants follow the assigned treatment strategy is of interest (1). Furthermore, as a measure of effect, we use the risk difference. To estimate the total risk difference, we use g-methods to adjust for confounding. Specifically, we consider both marginal structural models and the g-formula so that we can assess robustness with respect to different misspecifications. We fit the marginal structure model with inverse probability weighting (IPW) to adjust for confounding, by using the variables identified in the DAGs as suitable deconfounders. In the g-formula approach we fit a logistic regression including the deconfounding variables and subsequently use standardisation to evaluate the marginal population effect. To estimate valid confidence intervals, we use the bootstrap method (1).

Table 10. Primary, and subgroup analysis specification

A. Analysis – Outcome Breastfeeding

Hypothesis:	The higher the treatment (proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio care) the higher the probability for establishing exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge
Exposure contrast:	Dichotomous, 100% target nurse-to-patient ratio care until 24 hours before discharge from postnatal unit – yes / no (less than 100%)
Outcome:	Dichotomous, exclusive breastfeeding during the last 24 hours before discharge, yes / no
Analytic software:	R Version 4.3.3 in RStudio Version 2024.09.1 On Windows 10 22H2
Model(s): <i>(provide details or code)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marginal structural model fitted with IPW - Outcome model and standardisation to implement the g-formula <p>Outcome model: Logistic regression with the outcome as response and treatment plus the deconfounders as covariates. Confidence intervals for both approaches are derived by bootstrapping.</p>
Confounding adjustment method	<i>Name method and provide relevant details, e.g. bivariate, multivariable, propensity score matching (specify matching algorithm ratio and caliper), propensity score weighting (specify weight formula, trimming, truncation), propensity score stratification (specify strata definition), other.</i>
	Adjustment via IPW, where the exposure model is a logistic regression model with treatment as response variable and the deconfounders as covariates

	<p>IPW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - glm(exposure ~ Gestational age + Gestational age^2 + Citizenship + Language + Maternal age + Maternal age^2 + Parity + Parity^2 + Birth weight + Birth weight^2 + Risk of hypoglycaemia + Mode of birth + Labour complications + Pregnancy complications, family = binomial, data = data) <p>The weights obtained from the exposure model are used to fit a marginal structural model of the outcome as a saturated linear model which allows us to derive risks under each treatment value and evaluate the risk difference.</p> <p>Outcome model:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - glm(outcome ~ exposure + Gestational age + Gestational age^2 + Citizenship + Language + Maternal age + Maternal age^2 + Parity + Parity^2 + Birth weight + Birth weight^2 + Risk of hypoglycaemia + Mode of birth + Labour complications + Pregnancy complications, family = binomial, data = data) <p>Once fitted, the outcome model is used to predict potential outcomes under each treatment value for all records to implement a g-formula approach.</p>
Missing data methods	Name method and provide relevant details, e.g. missing indicators, complete case, last value carried forward, multiple imputation (specify model/variables), other.
	<p>Complete cases analysis.</p> <p>Descriptive comparison of the covariates' distributions between the excluded cases and the included cases, to qualitatively assess the extent to which the implementation of complete cases analysis may introduce selection bias.</p> <p>Comparison of the distributions of the exposure variables between the excluded and the included cases to assess the extent of a potential selection bias introduced by restricting the analysis to complete cases.</p>
Subgroup Analyses	List all subgroups

B. Analysis – Outcome Newborn

Hypothesis:	The higher the treatment (proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio care) the higher the probability for a healthy newborn at hospital discharge.
Exposure contrast:	Dichotomous, 100% target nurse-to-patient ratio care for the entire postnatal unit stay – yes / no (less than 100%)
Outcome:	Dichotomous, healthy newborn at hospital discharge, yes / no
Analytic software:	R Version 4.3.3 in RStudio Version 2024.09.1 On Windows 10 22H2
Model(s): <i>(provide details or code)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marginal structural model fitted with IPW - Outcome model and standardisation to implement the g-formula <p>Outcome model: Logistic regression with the outcome as response and treatment plus the deconfounders as covariates. Confidence intervals for both approaches are derived by bootstrapping.</p>

Confounding adjustment method	Name method and provide relevant details, e.g. bivariate, multivariable, propensity score matching (specify matching algorithm ratio and caliper), propensity score weighting (specify weight formula, trimming, truncation), propensity score stratification (specify strata definition), other.
	<p>Adjustment via IPW, where the exposure model is a logistic regression model with treatment as response variable and the deconfounders as covariates</p> <p>IPW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - glm(exposure ~ Gestational age + Gestational age^2 + Citizenship + Language + Maternal age + Maternal age^2 + Parity + Parity^2 + Birth weight + Birth weight^2 + Risk of hypoglycaemia + Mode of birth + Labour complications + Pregnancy complications + Feeding method, family = binomial, data = data) <p>The weights obtained from the exposure model are used to fit a marginal structural model of the outcome as a saturated linear model which allows us to derive risks under each treatment value and evaluate the risk difference.</p> <p>Outcome model:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - glm(outcome ~ exposure + Gestational age + Gestational age^2 + Citizenship + Language + Maternal age + Maternal age^2 + Parity + Parity^2 + Birth weight + Birth weight^2 + Risk of hypoglycaemia + Mode of birth + Labour complications + Pregnancy complications + Feeding method, family = binomial, data = data) <p>Once fitted, the outcome model is used to predict potential outcomes under each treatment value for all records to implement a g-formula approach.</p>
Missing data methods	Name method and provide relevant details, e.g. missing indicators, complete case, last value carried forward, multiple imputation (specify model/variables), other.
	<p>Complete cases analysis.</p> <p>Descriptive comparison of the covariates' distributions between the excluded cases and the included cases, to qualitatively assess the extent to which the implementation of complete cases analysis may introduce selection bias.</p> <p>Comparison of the distributions of the exposure variables between the excluded and the included cases to assess the extent of a potential selection bias introduced by restricting the analysis to complete cases.</p>
Subgroup Analyses	List all subgroups

Table 11. Sensitivity analyses – rationale, strengths and limitations

	What is being varied? How?	Why? (What do you expect to learn?)	Strengths of the sensitivity analysis compared to the primary	Limitations of the sensitivity analysis compared to the primary
Varying target nurse-to-patient ratios for exposure of interest	The target nurse-to-patient ratio is based on Australian regulations. There are no regulations in Switzerland. Different target ratios could result in differences for the effect.	It is an explorative approach to search for the optimal target ratio for the postnatal unit. If a different target ratio has a different effect, we might be able to define an optimal target ratio.	Other target ratios could be more suitable for postnatal care compared to the Australian regulations.	There are not really any other regulations recommended and therefore, the decision, which other target ratios should be investigated is rather arbitrary.

7.6. Data sources

7.6.1 Context and rationale for data sources

Reason for selection: “Some national data sources exist for inpatient cases, such as diagnoses and procedure codes. National data sources with information for the exposure do not exist, therefore it was necessary to use hospital data. To avoid burdening the already pressured hospital staff with prospective data collection for the study, the decision was taken to use routine hospital data with its advantages and disadvantages. Routine hospital data offers the opportunity to work with increased sample size and study duration. The data, however, is not collected for the study purpose specifically, and therefore, some variables might have an increased number of missing data points and others are not measured at all or cannot be extracted in a structured way.” (1)

Strengths of data source(s): “Large sample size, longitudinal data, matched parent-child data.” (1)

Limitations of data source(s): “Staffing and movement data are not controlled data and data entry is done by clinical staff. There is a higher chance of missing data compared to data collected for research purposes; and higher likelihood of wrong entries which limit the availability of complete cases.” (1)

The true nurse-to-patient ratio is not available with this data. Therefore, the exposure is calculated based on the total number of mothers and total number of RNs and RMs available at a certain point in time on the unit. The average ratio is used for all mothers for this time point.

Data source provenance/curation: “Some data sources (parts of Data 2, Data 3, Data 4) are collected for invoicing purposes and the federal statistical office, therefore this data is controlled for errors. Data 1 is collected for salary purposes (worked time), only unit leaders are allowed to change things and employees are asked to check for correctness because it has an influence on their direct salary. Some data sources need substantial cleaning (Data 1, parts of Data 2, Data 5), which is done by the study team in close collaboration with the clinical site. Possibility checks (e.g., longest working time; maternal age > 60) are done in all data sets but with a stronger focus on data sources that need substantial cleaning. Where questions arise regarding inconsistencies in the data, this will be discussed with the representatives from the clinical site (e.g., working time > 16 hours, cases with maternal age > 60).” (1)

Table 12. Metadata about data sources and software

	Data 1	Data 2	Data 3	Data 4	Data 5
Data Source(s):	PEP data (consisting of 7 different sheets)	Patient data (consisting of 6 different sheets)	Patient birth data (1 sheet)	FSO data (federal statistical office) (1 sheet)	Newborn EHR data (2 sheets)
Study Period:	01.01.2019 - 31.12.2022				
Eligible Cohort Entry Period:	01.01.2019 - 31.12.2022				
Data Version (or date of last update):	26.01.2023	14.05.2023	14.05.2023	07.06.2024	28.06.2024
Data sampling/extraction criteria:	Criteria: Time frame and target unit IDs	Criteria: Time frame and target unit IDs	Criteria: Time frame	Criteria: Time frame	Criteria: Time frame
Type(s) of data:	Staff roster system	Administrative claims	Clinical Data Warehouse	FSO	Clinical Data Warehouse
Data linkage:	Unit ID, Nurse ID, Date, Time	Unit ID, Patient ID, Case ID, Date, Time	Patient ID, Case ID	Patient ID, Case ID	Patient ID, Case ID
Conversion to CDM*:	No	No	No	No	No
Software for data management:	Preparation in Clinical Data Warehouse not reported. Extraction from Clinical Data Warehouse in R via SQL-Code Pseudonymisation of data in R on Windows 10. All further steps (data cleaning, linkage, analysis) in R on Windows 10.				

*CDM = Common Data Model, EHR = Electronic Health Record, FSO = Federal statistical office, PEP = roster system, ID = identifier, SQL = structured query language

7.7. Data management

Appendix C

7.8. Quality control

“Data quality will be cross-checked with hospital statistics, i.e., number of births, mode of births. Staff roster data will be cross-checked with the roster system user interface. Missing data will be assessed and reasons identified. Miscoded data will be checked with the medical coder from the clinical site. Algorithms to identify cases will be discussed with the medical coder and adjusted based on their recommendation.” (1)

7.9. Study size and feasibility

No prior study size calculations done.

Table 13. Power and sample size – N/A

No prior power calculation done.

8. Limitation of the methods

It is not possible to know exactly, how the nurse-to-patient ratio was applied during the shifts. It is likely that RNs / RMs with more complex cases are responsible for less mother-baby-dyads than others. This might reduce the effect measured, as some dyads might have received less than 100% care, even when the target ratio would have been possible.

The outcomes of interest are strongly dependent on the documentation quality of the RNs and RMs. During shifts with high workload, there might be missed documentation. Resulting in declaring a newborn healthy although it wasn't. Which would again reduce the effect measured.

9. Protection of human subjects

Appendix D (proposal for ethical review and decision from ethical board)

10. Reporting of adverse events

n/a

11. References

1. Eggenschwiler LC, Smith V, Moffa G, Simon M. Effect of midwifery staffing on the occurrence of spontaneous vaginal birth and use of pain medication – a target trial emulation protocol. Zenodo [Internet]. 2025 Jan 31; Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14677135>
2. Wang SV, Pottegård A, Crown W, Arlett P, Ashcroft DM, Benchimol EI, et al. HARmonized Protocol Template to Enhance Reproducibility of hypothesis evaluating real-world evidence studies on treatment effects: A good practices report of a joint ISPE/ISPOR task force. *Pharmacoepidemiology and Drug Safety* [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2024 Apr 23];32(1):44–55. Available from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/pds.5507>
3. Dani C, Papini S, Iannuzzi L, Pratesi S. Midwife-to-newborn ratio and neonatal outcome in healthy term infants. *Acta Paediatr.* 2020;109(9):1787–90.
4. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence. Safe midwifery staffing for maternity settings (NG4) [Internet]. London: NICE; 2015. Available from: <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ng4>
5. The Parliament of Victoria. Safe Patient Care (Nurse to Patient and Midwife to Patient Ratios) Act 2015 [Internet]. Jul 1, 2022. Available from: <https://www.legislation.vic.gov.au/in-force/acts/safe-patient-care-nurse-patient-and-midwife-patient-ratios-act-2015/009>
6. Association of Women’s Health, Obstetric and Neonatal Nurses (AWOHNN). Standards for Professional Registered Nurse Staffing for Perinatal Units. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic & Neonatal Nursing* [Internet]. 2022 Jul 1 [cited 2023 Jul 20];51(4):S5–98. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0884217522000090>
7. Victora CG, Bahl R, Barros AJD, França GVA, Horton S, Krasevec J, et al. Breastfeeding in the 21st century: epidemiology, mechanisms, and lifelong effect. *The Lancet* [Internet]. 2016 Jan 30 [cited 2025 Mar 18];387(10017):475–90. Available from: [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736\(15\)01024-7/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736(15)01024-7/fulltext)
8. Rollins NC, Bhandari N, Hajeebhoy N, Horton S, Lutter CK, Martines JC, et al. Why invest, and what it will take to improve breastfeeding practices? *The Lancet* [Internet]. 2016 Jan 30 [cited 2025 Mar 18];387(10017):491–504. Available from: [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736\(15\)01044-2/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736(15)01044-2/fulltext)
9. World Health Organization. Global strategy for infant and young child feeding [Internet]. 2003 [cited 2025 Mar 18]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9241562218>
10. Cohen SS, Alexander DD, Krebs NF, Young BE, Cabana MD, Erdmann P, et al. Factors Associated with Breastfeeding Initiation and Continuation: A Meta-Analysis. *The Journal of Pediatrics* [Internet]. 2018 Dec 1 [cited 2024 Jun 22];203:190-196.e21. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022347618311181>
11. Bürger B, Schindler K, Tripolt T, Griesbacher A, Stüger HP, Wagner KH, et al. Factors Associated with (Exclusive) Breastfeeding Duration—Results of the SUKIE-Study. *Nutrients* [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2023 Mar 7];14(9):1704. Available from: <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-6643/14/9/1704>
12. World Health Organization. WHO recommendations on maternal and newborn care for a positive postnatal experience [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2025 Mar 18]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240045989>
13. Talisman S, Guedalia J, Farkash R, Avitan T, Srebnik N, Kasirer Y, et al. Neonatal intensive care admission for term neonates and subsequent childhood mortality: a retrospective linkage study. *BMC Medicine* [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2023 Nov 17];21(1):44. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-023-02744-7>

14. Schulzke S, Das-Kundu S, Fontijn J, Mönkhoff M, Neumann R, Szinnai G. Leitlinie zur Prävention und Therapie der Hypoglykämie bei Neugeborenen ab 35+0 Schwangerschaftswochen auf der Wochenbettstation. *Paediatrica* [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2023 Aug 23];32(1):24–8. Available from: https://www.paediatricschweiz.ch/?p=36301&preview=true&_thumbnail_id=38747
15. Lyndon A, Simpson KR, Spetz J, Zhong J, Gay CL, Fletcher J, et al. Nurse-Reported Staffing Guidelines and Exclusive Breast Milk Feeding. *Nursing Research* [Internet]. 2022 Sep 5 [cited 2023 Mar 22];71(6):432–40. Available from: <https://journals.lww.com/10.1097/NNR.0000000000000620>
16. Eggenschwiler LC, Moffa G, Smith V, Simon M. Perinatal midwifery care demand in a tertiary hospital: A time-series analysis. *International Journal of Nursing Studies Advances* [Internet]. 2025 Jun 1 [cited 2025 Jan 27];8:100299. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666142X25000098>
17. Rissanen ARS, Gissler M, Nupponen IK, Nuutila ME, Jernman RM. Perinatal outcome of dichorionic and monochorionic-diamniotic Finnish twins: a historical cohort study. *Acta Obstetrica et Gynecologica Scandinavica* [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2025 Apr 8];101(1):153–62. Available from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/aogs.14285>
18. Sandall J, Murrells T, Dodwell M, Gibson R, Bewley S, Coxon K, et al. The efficient use of the maternity workforce and the implications for safety and quality in maternity care: a population-based, cross-sectional study. *Health Services and Delivery Research*. 2014 Oct;2(38):1–266.
19. Sandall J, Turienzo CF, Devane D, Soltani H, Gillespie P, Gates S, et al. Midwife continuity of care models versus other models of care for childbearing women. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 Apr 18];(4). Available from: <https://www.cochranelibrary.com/cdsr/doi/10.1002/14651858.CD004667.pub6/full>
20. Turner L, Griffiths P, Kitson-Reynolds E. Midwifery and nurse staffing of inpatient maternity services – A systematic scoping review of associations with outcomes and quality of care. *Midwifery* [Internet]. 2021 Dec [cited 2022 Oct 11];103:103118. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0266613821001984>
21. UNICEF. Baby-Friendly Hospital Initiative [Internet]. [cited 2025 Mar 23]. Available from: <https://www.unicef.org/documents/baby-friendly-hospital-initiative>
22. World Health Organization. Implementation guidance: protecting, promoting and supporting breastfeeding in facilities providing maternity and newborn services – the revised Baby-friendly Hospital Initiative [Internet]. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2018 [cited 2025 Mar 23]. Available from: <https://www.unicef.org/documents/baby-friendly-hospital-initiative>
23. Anthony R, McKinlay CJD. Adaptation for life after birth: a review of neonatal physiology. *Anaesthesia & Intensive Care Medicine* [Internet]. 2023 Jan 1 [cited 2025 Mar 23];24(1):1–9. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1472029922002715>
24. Harding JE, Alsweller JM, Edwards TE, McKinlay CJ, Gough L. Neonatal hypoglycaemia. *bmjmed* [Internet]. 2024 Apr 9 [cited 2024 Nov 8];3(1). Available from: <https://bmjmedicine.bmj.com/content/3/1/e000544>
25. Ferguson KD, McCann M, Katikireddi SV, Thomson H, Green MJ, Smith DJ, et al. Evidence synthesis for constructing directed acyclic graphs (ESC-DAGs): a novel and systematic method for building directed acyclic graphs. *International Journal of Epidemiology*. 2020;49(1):322–9.
26. Textor J, Hardt J, Knüppel S. DAGitty: A Graphical Tool for Analyzing Causal Diagrams. *Epidemiology* [Internet]. 2011 Sep [cited 2021 Apr 13];22(5):745. Available from: https://journals.lww.com/epidem/Fulltext/2011/09000/DAGitty__A_Graphical_Tool_for_Analyzing_Causal.22.aspx
27. Textor J, van der Zander B, Gilthorpe MS, Liśkiewicz M, Ellison GT. Robust causal inference using directed acyclic graphs: the R package 'dagitty'. *International Journal of Epidemiology* [Internet]. 2016 Dec 1 [cited 2025 Jan 15];45(6):1887–94. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyw341>

12. Appendices

12.1. Appendix A – Codes for variables from routine data

Characteristic	Details	Code Type	Diagnosis Position	Code list	Data ¹
Exposure					
Staffing exposure	Target nurse-to-patient ratio ≥ 1 vs. Target nurse-to-patient ratio < 1 Calculated as a shift-level mean over the whole follow-up time	n/a	n/a	Presence on postnatal unit (unit-id)	Data1 (Nurse information) Data2 (Patient information)
Outcomes					
Exclusive Breastfeeding within last 24 hours before hospital discharge	Feeding entries within the last 24 hours before discharge need all be breastfeeding	EHR	n/a	OrderText = 239	Data2 (Discharge information) Data5 (Feeding)
Healthy newborn at hospital discharge	All temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), glucose (mmol/L), and bilirubin (mmol/L) entries are within the norm. No separation from mother (due to admission to NICU)	EHR	n/a	Meona = ME051 (Temperature) OrderText = 16 (Glucose) OrderText = 246 (Bilirubin)	Data2 (Movement information) Data5 (EHR)
	Hyperbilirubinaemia based on initiation of phototherapy, because bilirubin thresholds are not unified	CHOP	Any	CHOP22 Code: 99.83	Data2
Inclusion criteria					
Mother admitted to the postnatal unit for early postpartum	Admission to the postnatal unit directly after birth from labour ward	ICD10-GM	Any	ICD10-GM Code: Z37.0 ICD10-GM Code: Z37.2 ICD10-GM Code: Z37.3 ICD10-GM Code: Z37.5 ICD10-GM Code: Z37.6	Data2

¹Data1 = PEP, Data2 = Claims data, Data3 = Birth data, Data4 = FSO data, NICU = neonatal intensive care unit

Characteristic	Details	Code Type	Diagnosis Position	Code list	Data ¹
Newborn admitted to the postnatal unit for early postpartum	Admission to the postnatal unit directly after birth from labour ward	ICD10-GM	Any	ICD10-GM Code: Z38.0 ICD10-GM Code: Z38.3 ICD10-GM Code: Z38.6	Data2
Exclusion criteria					
Readmission	Second admission to the postnatal unit	n/a	n/a	Different case id than the one assigned at birth	Data2 Data3
Stillbirth	ICD10-GM codes for birth of a non-living child	ICD10-GM	Any	ICD10-GM Code: Z37.1 ICD10-GM Code: Z37.3 ICD10-GM Code: Z37.4 ICD10-GM Code: Z37.6 ICD10-GM Code: Z37.7	Data2
Suppressed lactation [only for outcome breastfeeding]	ICD10-GM code for suppressed lactation	ICD10-GM	Any	ICD10-GM Code: O92.50	Data2
Maternal age <18 years	Minor mothers are excluded; Measurement at time of labour ward admission; Time 0 – maternal date of birth	n/a	n/a	Maternal date of birth	Data2
Mother-baby-dyad always together	Transfer times are equal between mother and newborn	n/a	n/a	Time stamp of transfer to postnatal unit are equal between mother and newborn	Data2
Multiple birth	ICD10-GM codes for twins, triplets and more	ICD10-GM	Any	ICD10-GM Code: O30.0 ICD10-GM Code: O30.1 ICD10-GM Code: O30.2 ICD10-GM Code: O30.8 ICD10-GM Code: O30.9	Data2
Covariates					
Admission to NICU	Neonatal intensive care unit admission (currently mediator)	SwissDRG	Any	DRG Version 11 Code: P60C	Data2
Birth weight	Weight measured directly after birth in grams	EHR	n/a	Birth weight entered in EHR	Data3
Breastfeeding initiation within 1 hour after birth	First breastfeeding entry within 1 hour after birth (Moderator)	EHR	n/a	OrderText = 239	Data2 Data5 (Feeding)

Characteristic	Details	Code Type	Diagnosis Position	Code list	Data ¹
Cold season	Outside temperature during hospital stay (Moderator)	n/a	n/a	Not measured	-
Country of birth / ethnicity {Citizenship}	Country where the person currently has citizenship (self-reported)	n/a	n/a	Citizenship	Data2
Country of birth / ethnicity {Language}	Self-reported primary language	n/a	n/a	Language	Data2
Early skin-to-skin contact after birth	Direct skin-to-skin contact after birth (Moderator, not measured)	n/a	n/a	Not measured	-
Feeding method	Newborn feeding method in the labour ward	EHR	n/a	OrderText = 239	Data2 Data5 (Feeding)
Gestational age	Gestational age in number of days	FSO	Any	FSO Variable Number: 2.3.V02 FSO Variable Number: 2.3.V03	Data4
Labour complications	Complications such as complicated perineal tear; prolonged labour; postnatal haemorrhage	ICD10-GM	Any	ICD10-GM Code: 070.2 ICD10-GM Code: 070.3 ICD10-GM Code: 063.0 ICD10-GM Code: 063.2 ICD10-GM Code: 063.9 ICD10-GM Code: 072.0 ICD10-GM Code: 072.1 ICD10-GM Code: 072.2 ICD10-GM Code: 072.3 ICD10-GM Code: 073.0 ICD10-GM Code: 073.1 ICD10-GM Code: 071.0 ICD10-GM Code: 071.1 ICD10-GM Code: 071.2 ICD10-GM Code: 071.3	Data2
Length of stay	Duration of entry to postnatal unit until discharge in days (currently mediator)	n/a	n/a	Admission to postnatal unit – Discharge from postnatal unit	Data2
Level of education	Categories based on level of education (Moderator, not measured)	n/a	n/a	Not measured	-

Characteristic	Details	Code Type	Diagnosis Position	Code list	Data ¹
Maternal age	Age: Time 0 - date of birth/365	n/a	n/a	Maternal date of birth	Data2
Mode of birth	Mode of birth	ICD10-GM CHOP	Any	ICD10-GM Code: O80 CHOP22 Code: 73.59 ICD10-GM Code: O81 ICD10-GM Code: O32.1 CHOP22 Code: 72.01 CHOP22 Code: 72.09 CHOP22 Code: 72.11 CHOP22 Code: 72.19 CHOP22 Code: 72.21 CHOP22 Code: 72.29 CHOP22 Code: 72.31 CHOP22 Code: 72.39 CHOP22 Code: 72.4 CHOP22 Code: 72.51 CHOP22 Code: 72.52 CHOP22 Code: 72.53 CHOP22 Code: 72.54 CHOP22 Code: 72.6 CHOP22 Code: 72.71 CHOP22 Code: 72.79 CHOP22 Code: 72.9 ICD10-GM Code: O82 CHOP22 Code: 74.1X.10 CHOP22 Code: 74.2X.10 CHOP22 Code: 74.4X.10 CHOP22 Code: 74.99.10 CHOP22 Code: 74.0X.00 CHOP22 Code: 74.1X.00 CHOP22 Code: 74.2X.00 CHOP22 Code: 74.4X.00 CHOP22 Code: 74.0X.20 CHOP22 Code: 74.1X.20 CHOP22 Code: 74.2X.20	Data2

Characteristic	Details	Code Type	Diagnosis Position	Code list	Data ¹
				CHOP22 Code: 74.4X.20 CHOP22 Code: 74.0X.99 CHOP22 Code: 74.1X.99 CHOP22 Code: 74.2X.99 CHOP22 Code: 74.4X.99 CHOP22 Code: 74.3	
Parity	Number of children born exclusive of this birth	FSO	n/a	FSO Variable Number: 2.3.V05	Data4
Peak total serum bilirubin	Highest measured total serum bilirubin value in the newborn in mmol/L (Moderator)	EHR	n/a	OrderText = 246 (Bilirubin)	Data5
Phototherapy	Phototherapy initiated on the postnatal unit (Moderator)	CHOP	Any	CHOP22 Code: 99.83	Data2
Pregnancy complications	Complications such as any kind of diabetes, all hypertensive disorders	ICD10-GM	Any	ICD10-GM Code: 024.0 ICD10-GM Code: 024.1 ICD10-GM Code: 024.2 ICD10-GM Code: 024.3 ICD10-GM Code: 024.4 ICD10-GM Code: 024.9 ICD10GM Code: 010.0 ICD10GM Code: 010.1 ICD10GM Code: 010.2 ICD10GM Code: 010.3 ICD10GM Code: 010.4 ICD10GM Code: 010.9 ICD10GM Code: 011 ICD10GM Code: 013 ICD10GM Code: 014.0 ICD10GM Code: 014.1 ICD10GM Code: 014.2 ICD10GM Code: 014.9 ICD10GM Code: 015.0 ICD10GM Code: 015.1 ICD10GM Code: 015.2 ICD10GM Code: 015.9 ICD10GM Code: 016	Data2

Characteristic	Details	Code Type	Diagnosis Position	Code list	Data ¹
Risk of hyperbilirubinaemia	Different reasons for risk of hyperbilirubinaemia (Moderator, not measured)	n/a	n/a	Not measured	-
Risk of hypoglycaemia	Neonatal risk of hypoglycaemia due to different reasons. Identified through proxy of feeding intervention.	EHR	n/a	OrderText = 239	Data5 (Feeding)
Risk of hypothermia	Different reasons for risk of hypothermia (Moderator, not measured)	n/a	n/a	Not measured	-
Time of birth	Day time vs. nighttime (Moderator)	n/a	n/a	Time of birth	Data3

12.2. Appendix B – DAG assessment protocols

12.3. Appendix C – Data management plan

12.4. Appendix D – Ethical proposal and decision letter